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TECHNO-ECONOMIC OPTIMIZATION OF STEAM CRACKER'S STEAM NETWORK

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Abstract

Challenging market environment, tightening customers' requirements as well as commitment to reduce the environmental impact make the energy efficiency a very actual topic. In the petrochemical industry, energy costs are the second largest expenditure right after the feedstock. Examined Steam Cracker's (SC) steam network in SLOVNAFT refinery operates on six steam pressure levels and allows operating as a standalone network or import, alternatively export, steam from/to outer network. Outer steam network is fed by steam from Combined Heat and Power Unit (CHP) as well as from secondary steam sources located in the refinery. This layout complexity and operation flexibility offers the possibility for overall techno-economic optimization reflecting both technical limitations and actual economic situation. This study provides a brief comparison of its operation before and after debottlenecking (implementation of regulation valve) and shows the importance of proper regulation possibility. Annual savings resulting from debottlenecking reach up to 1 million € and the simple payback period is less than 1 year. Propriate key performance indicators (KPI) were also determined to assess the overall steam network performance as to maximize energy efficiency and savings.

Introduction

Efficient, safe, and economic operation of industrial steam and power systems belongs to key issues when speaking about industrial energy efficiency^{1,2}. Especially in refineries³, petrochemical plants^{4,5}, and fertilizer production units⁶ such systems are deeply process-integrated, as the substantial amounts of steam produced on-site are usually consumed in general purpose steam turbines driving key process equipment. Steam on three to five main pressure levels is commonly produced and utilized in such plants^{7,8}, where individual levels are fed from extractions from steam drives or from their backpressure, being complemented by let-down stations serving as regulation buffer. Such deeply intertwined plants can be viewed, modeled, and optimized as polygeneration units⁹, where only a coupled energetic, economic, and environmental approach to their operation optimization ensures a sustainable development^{10,11}.

More specifically, steam crackers (or ethylene plants) usually produce very high pressure (over 10 MPa) steam both in convection sections of cracking furnaces and in a separate steam boiler¹². Produced steam is used in extraction-condensing turbines driving key process compressors, while the extracted steam is used in process and in smaller steam drives, resulting in a system of up to five main pressure levels¹³. As such plants are often integrated in a larger industrial cluster, steam export to and import from adjacent production units is possible, offering significant space for cost optimization and for utilization of possible synergies^{14,15}. Moreover, such interconnections increase the system flexibility, offering extra space to cope with variable seasonal heat demand. Their exploitation is often the key point of various optimization studies that are published nowadays, stressing the need for unified and efficient steam network management within the whole industrial cluster¹⁶⁻¹⁸. Bearing this in mind a study on operational costs reduction of steam system in a steam cracker integrated in a refinery-petrochemical cluster SLOVNAFT was conducted with the aim of simultaneous cost and carbon footprint reduction and of energy efficiency increase. This study follows our previous activities related to optimization of steam networks and cutting down operational expenses of refinery units¹⁹⁻²¹. At the same time, it intends to highlight the contribution of industrial innovation and optimization to industrial energy efficiency increase and greenhouse gases emissions reduction in the Middle European area^{22,23}.

Study objectives

The aims of this contribution are in particular:

- To analyze existing SC's steam network with focus on technical limitations of selected KPI.
- To assemble benefit calculation methodology after implementation of new let-down valve.
- To utilize obtained data and methodology as a basis for a new real-time optimizer in order to secure optimal regulation and economic results.

Description of steam crackers' steam system

The Steam Cracker (SC) in SLOVNAFT refinery has a complex steam system, that can act as a standalone system or, if needed, is able to import or export steam from/to outer steam network. The steam network operates on six different pressure levels with typical parameters:

- SS steam: 11.0 MPa (g), 520 °C
- HS steam: 3.5 MPa (g), 350 °C
- MS steam: 1.2 MPa (g), 250 °C
- LS steam: 0.4 MPa (g), 170 °C
- PS steam: 0.25 MPa (g), 138 °C
- DS steam: 0.7 MPa, 190 °C

SS steam is produced internally in cracking furnaces and in an auxiliary steam boiler. The shares used to be almost equal in the past, as shown in Fig. 1. However, the share of process steam increased in the recent years, both due to increased SC feedstock processing (2017 – 2019) and due to energy saving measures described in this contribution (2020).

Figure 1. Annual SS steam production and ethylene production from 2013 to 2020 (Ethylene production is intentionally omitted since it belongs to business sensitive data).

The SS steam is consumed in combined extraction-condensing steam drives driving process gas compressors. Excess steam is reduced on let-down station to HS steam. Similarly, HS and MS steam is used to drive various steam drives and the rest is reduced to lower pressure level steam. The LS steam is used mostly as a heating medium in fractionators, boiler feed water (BFW) preparation or steam tracing. Moreover, HS, MS and LS steam export or import are possible; however, only HS and LS steam import is usually utilized. PS steam is produced by LS steam reduction and is utilized as heating medium in few heat exchangers and vessels. The DS steam is used directly in the process as a dilution steam added directly into the feedstock.

Fig. 2 shows the consumption of SS steam. Steam-drives consumption varies according to SC feed rate, naturally. On the other hand, there was almost constant SS steam reduction share in the past years.

Constant share of steam reduction is the first indication of non-functional regulation element. And really, the let-down valve "A" lost its regulation ability due erosion under extreme conditions of SS steam. The valve opening was rather constant at 14 % before turnaround in 2019 and yet the steam inlet flow varied a lot, as shown in Fig. 3.

External energy audit performed in 2013 recommended installation of parallel let-down valve with smaller capacity and independent regulation to ensure smooth and functional regulation of SS steam network. This was in line with best practice, recommending reducing the amount of steam flowing through let-down stations to minimum. Preliminary analysis found two possible benefits:

- Direct fuel (natural gas) saving due more efficient HS steam production by extraction instead of steam reduction. Thus, improved energy efficiency of SC and whole SLOVNAFT is expected. Moreover, less CO₂ emissions will be produced.
- Enabled HS and LS steam import due less steam being reduced internally. Imported steam is usually produced from cheaper fuel (mixed petroleum residue, MPR, that is usually in excess). Additional extraction electricity generation would be possible thanks to increased steam supply from CHP unit. These effects contribute to better economic results. On the other hand, there is negative CO₂ effect

accompanied with MPR fuel utilization since the CO₂ specific production factor of MPR is higher than of natural gas. Increased steam supply from CHP unit is thus in contrary with the shift towards cleaner fuels^{24,25} proposed to lower the industrial carbon footprint but is justified from economic point of view.

Figure 2. Annual SS steam consumption and ethylene production from 2013 to 2020 (Ethylene production is intentionally omitted, since it was evaluated as business sensitive information).

Figure 3. Let-down valve "A" opening and steam inlet flow before turnaround 2019.

New parallel let-down valve "B" was installed in turnaround 2019. Lower steam throughput allows two-zone regulation. Valve "B" is utilized at lower steam inlet flows, usually below 30 t/h. Above this threshold, "A" valve takes over the control.

The impact of new "B" valve installation can be observed in Fig. 2 showing significant SS steam reduction decrease in 2020 as well as in Fig. 4, showing the opening of valves "A" and "B" after turnaround 2019. "B" valve is used as a replacement of "A" valve, except non-standard operational states (unit shut-down/start-up, etc.).

Figure 4. Let-down valves' opening and SS steam reduction after turnaround 2019.

Real-time optimizer development

Functional regulation element suddenly offers higher flexibility in steam operation. Steam import due decreased steam reduction and the resulting benefits were possible; however, there was no decision support tool to say what to do in order to get optimal economic performance.

The methodology is based on savings calculation compared to baseline. The baseline determined based on filtered field data from 2017 to 2019 represents typical operation before turnaround 2019. The aim was to select valid data corresponding to a steady operational state without ongoing furnace decoking, when the SS steam reduction is higher. Few issues had to be solved in order to get a proper data set, e.g. steam inlet flow calculation based on valve opening (at low steam flows), missing data refill, etc. Benefit calculation methodology compilation required the knowledge of used hardware, therefore steam drives' performance curves and lots of technical documentation was needed. Internal and external energy pricing list was inevitable element as well.

Subsequently, an in-house built real-time optimizing tool was developed using the benefit calculation methodology. Limits were added to KPI occurring in the calculation to evaluate gaps. The tool compares the actual benefit with the highest possible benefit in every single moment and calculates the optimal steam balance with respect to set limits of KPI.

Fig. 5 shows the model decision tree. There are two directions that the model can decide for. Either the steam import or steam extraction are preferred. The decision depends on the benefit belonging to increased steam import or extraction. If the decision is to maximize steam extraction, four different operational states (State 1 to 4) can occur, depending on the actual conditions. Gap on steam let-down station (the actual steam flow vs. the maximal steam flow) is compared to gaps on steam extraction, import and export. Four states are defined also for steam import maximization (State 5 to 8). In that case, gap on steam let-down station is the key parameter. The objective is to achieve optimal steam balance with the highest benefit. Each state defines targets for SS steam reduction and extraction as well as HS and LS steam import. The output of the real-time optimizer is the definition of KPI values. The rest is up to the energy controllers and operators.

Results

Implementation and fine-tuning phase were finished in April 2020. Since the very first year of evaluation, the 12-month cumulative benefit exceeded 1 million Euro. Exact numbers are not shown here, since they are subject to company data protection. The average natural gas savings since May 2020 reached 8.04 GJ/h and additional 25.02 GJ/h of natural gas is replaced by MPR utilization at TPP on average. Moreover, 0.92 MW of additional electricity was generated on average. The resulting payback period is approx. 3 months. Fig. 6 shows variable monthly benefit distribution, that demonstrates the continuing active steam network management. Moreover, involvement of operators results in the overall potential utilization close to 100 % in most time periods whereby the importance of human assets in overcoming barriers to industrial energy efficiency is documented^{26,27}.

Figure 5. Real-time optimizer model decision tree.

Figure 6. Monthly benefit utilization and composition.

The presented real time optimizing tool found its application in everyday practice. Its decisions help the operators to react on changing operational conditions and market environment.

The benefit calculation benefit includes CO₂ effect, whose importance is rapidly increasing in the recent period. The interesting fact is, that steam network optimization and increased steam import to SC are accompanied with CO₂ emissions production increase. Monthly balance depends on the ratio of steam import and steam extraction, but a net increase by 0.26 % of SC CO₂ emission production is observed on average. There is a positive economic result related to optimization, but on the other hand, the negative environmental impact in contrary to SLOVNAFT's long-term strategy of CO₂ emissions reduction. Sharply increasing carbon price and therefore increasing charges might outweigh the benefits from MPR utilization. It is likely that the model decisions will change under the influence of carbon prices.

Conclusions

The main goal of this contribution was to perform detailed analysis of existing SC's steam network to develop benefit calculation methodology and to set targets for subsequent optimization using in-house built real-time optimizer. The analysis confirmed lost regulation ability of SS steam let-down station and therefore of the whole steam network. Recovered regulation ability after implementation of 2013's energy audit proposal, installation of parallel let-down valve, has created a need for optimizing tool to maximize economic related to this project.

The analysis was also helpful to set targets necessary for correct setting of the optimizer. Let-down valve installation and subsequent steam network optimization have yielded interesting economic benefits resulting in a simple payback period in the magnitude of months. The KPI are monitored on a daily basis to ensure optimal performance.

During the project evaluation, an interesting fact was revealed. There is a benefit related to substitution of natural gas by MPR; however, it is coupled with increased overall CO₂ emission production. That is the opposite to SLOVNAFT's long-term strategy of carbon footprint reduction. Since the business driving force is the economy, changes in steam network regulation due to environmental issues are not expected; however, sharply increasing carbon prices may have significant impact soon.

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